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EVALUATION OF THE PERSPECTIVES OF PRESCHOOL TEACHERS WHO HAVE STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS IN THEIR CLASSROOM ON ETHICS

S. Sunay Yildirim Doğru

Dokuz Eylül University

s.y.dogru@gmail.com

H. Bilge Doğru

Dokuz Eylül University

dogru.b.h@gmail.com

Abstract

Teachers have to communicate with other people as a part of necessity and structure of their occupation. Therefore, just like other occupations that depend on human relations, teachers face situations that create ethical dilemma. In this research, determining the relationship between demographic informations (The institution where teachers work, their duties in the institution, their gender, age, the educational institution they graduated from and their length of service) and the thoughts about the professional ethical principles of the special education department and preschool education teachers was aimed. The design of the research was survey type research. First of all, relevant literature was reviewed and the data was collected with “The Professional Ethical Principles For Teacher Scale” which was developed by Kepenek in 2008. The scale was prepared in a 5-point Likert type. The sample of the study consists of 76 people, including teachers working in special education classes and students of special education departments. Because of the Pandemic, data was collected in online environment. Obtained data from marked questionnaires were subjected to statistical analysis with the SPSS package program. As a result of the research, it was found that preschool teachers are less aware of ethical rules. Thus, adding ethic topics to teacher training programs can be suggested to contribute to increase the quality of teacher education.

Keywords: *Ethics, Professional Ethics, Preschool Teacher, Special Education.*

Introduction

Ethics is very essential in human life from solving daily life problems to establishing values. Today, the concept of ethics is seen as a discipline that examines and regulates behavior patterns in business life (MEB, 2006). Ethics, as a part of practical philosophy, deals with human actions and their products (Flew, 2005). The word ethics has two different uses. First use; Habit carries the meaning of custom and tradition (MEB, 2006). In the second usage (this is the general usage), the person who acts and acts does not apply the transferred action rules and value measures without questioning; on the contrary, it is the person who turns them into habits in order to realize the desired good by grasping and thinking about it (MEB, 2006). The concept of ethics mostly includes certain behaviors, rules and norms developed for special groups (Arslan, 2018). Among the origins of ethics will be both our own wishes, our own expectations, our own satisfaction, and what the society finds “good-right-appropriate” will be important (MEB, 2006). The value judgments of social institutions also represent the “social origins of ethics” (MEB, 2006). In this sense, it talks about the ethical rules and ethical understanding of family, lawyer, religion, school, business, neighborhood, trade, humanity, profession, politics, medicine, media, press, capital market (etc.) (MEB, 2006). The approaches based on the development of ethical principles are the principles of equity, human rights, utilitarianism and individuality (MEB, 2006). Equity emphasizes that all decisions are consistent, impartial and factual (MEB, 2006). Human rights emphasize the existence, integrity and fundamental human rights of individuals (MEB, 2006). Ethical rules concern all segments of society. Our study is based on the professional ethics dimension. The sum of ethical principles and standards that guide and guide behavior in business life is called “professional ethics” (MEB, 2006). It is the professional principles of a certain occupational group that command members of the profession, force them to behave with certain rules, limit their personal tendencies, exclude incompetent and unprincipled members from the profession, regulate professional competition and aim to protect service ideals (MEB, 2006). What a professional member does is of interest to other colleagues after a point (MEB, 2006). Occupations are necessary for humans to continue their life. It is vital for all occupations to work in line with their stated purposes, to meet the material and spiritual needs of people (MEB, 2006). To achieve these goals, professional ethics are beneficial. Professional ethics is based on the principle that every member of the profession should be as good as possible (Ayдын, 2002; Baydar, 2005; Bir, 2019).

Also, Professional ethics help people to achieve their at work places. Ethics is especially important in a field that shapes other people's lives, such as the teaching profession. The teacher should have fair, empathetic, sensitive, adaptable behaviors and ideas that enable him to have the concept of teaching in the real sense (NEA, 2011). Many individuals in the society; As a family, as a friend, as a teacher, and as an administrator, they are faced with individuals with disabilities (Cavkaytar, 2017). Integration of individuals with special needs in society and gaining independent living skills depend on meeting their educational needs in line with their needs and individual differences (Deniz & Çoban, 2019). Therefore, teachers have a great responsibility. A series of integrative activities are needed in order to ensure that individuals with special needs integrate into social life more easily and effectively and the most important part of these activities is training activities (Deniz & Çoban, 2019). Individuals with special needs should receive education together with their peers with special needs as early as possible. In this regard, Diken and Batu' (2015) stated that effective inclusive education is integrated with the general education program of the school and in an environment accessible to all students; They stated that normally developing children, children with special needs, parents, school personnel and general education classes can be provided by preparing for inclusive education and working in cooperation (Deniz & Çoban, 2019). The study by Moreno et al. (2015) states that more teacher training is required for inclusive education to be effective and beneficial for all students (Girgin, 2021). In another study by Akçamete et al. (2016); Unethical behaviors faced by teachers working in the field of special education: "Providing services for those who do not receive vocational education and those with insufficient vocational education, providing financial benefits in the first place, not providing equal opportunities to students, not considering the expectations and needs of the family, giving wrong information to the family, ignoring the family's ignorance and exploiting their feelings, not respecting the family, etc." way it emerges (Özdemir, 2022). Unethical behaviors that arise in this way can sometimes cause undesirable consequences such as "violence against students" or "other parents' reaction to the mainstreaming student" (Özdemir, 2022).

In addition to their professional responsibilities, teachers also need to have ethical responsibilities. However, it is unfortunately not known how much the teachers consider the ethical phenomenon while performing their duties, and whether they question their ethical suitability while producing solutions to the dilemmas they encounter during their daily routines. In addition, it is thought that it can be a source for the creation of the ethical principles we have mentioned about the teaching

profession. In this context, it is aimed to determine the relationship between the opinions of preschool teachers, who have inclusion students in their class, on professional ethical principles and their demographic characteristics (the institution where the teachers work, their duties in the institution, their gender, age, the educational institution they graduated from, and their length of service).

Hypothesis of The Study: There are three hypothesis of the study.

- Majority of the score of the preschool teachers who have students with special needs in their classroom, from Teaching Professional Ethics Principles Scale is going to higher than the 50% of the highest possible score that can obtained from the questionnaire.

- Gender does not have an effect on the scores obtained form teachers.
- Age does not have an effect on the scores obtained form teachers.

Method

Model of the Study: A descriptive survey model, which is one of the quantitative research methods, was used in order to reveal the general situation in order to determine the importance that special education teachers and teacher candidates attach to professional ethical principles and their level of practice.

Study Group: The sample group of the research consists of preschool teachers who have inclusion students in their classes and who work in a public or private educational institution. 76 teachers working in preschool education classes were included in the sample of the study. 42 of the sample group are female and 34 are male. The age distribution of the sample group is; 47 are 20-30 years old, 21 are 31-40 years old, 6 are 41-50 years old, and only 2 are 51 years old and over.

Data Collection: The research is a survey type research and firstly the relevant literature was scanned, then the data was used on the “Teaching Professional Ethics Principles Scale” developed by Kepenek (2008). The scale is prepared in 5-point Likert type and consists of 28 questions. In addition, the personal information form prepared by the researcher was applied with the measurement tool. Personal Information Form; It is a form that aims to obtain information about the demographic characteristics of teachers. Gender, age, educational status, professional seniority, institution they work for, status of having an ethics committee duty in the institution they work in. The data were collected through online interviews as it was the pandemic period.

Ethical Principles of the Teaching Profession Scale: In this study, the scale prepared by Kepenek (2008) was used to determine the level of compliance with the ethical principles of the teaching profession. Ethical principles of teaching profession in scale; Nine dimensions were used: justice, honesty, respect, trust, professional responsibility, professional competence, human rights, love and organizational commitment (Kepenek, 2008). In order to measure these dimensions, 28 questions were prepared (Kepenek, 2008). The scale has a 5-point Likert-type rating as “1- never”, “2- rarely”, “3- sometimes”, “4- often” and “5- always” and the response time is approximately 10 minutes (Kepenek, 2008). Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to determine the reliability of the scale and the reliability value was obtained as 0.92 (Kepenek, 2008).

Analysis of Data: Data was analyzed with using SPSS 22.0 software. The total scores of teachers which were obtained from “Teaching Professional Ethics Principles Scale” were measured and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was done for normality testing. According to the result, it is found that data from the sample was not distributed normally. Thus, to test hypothesis, Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test was made and the differences between the total scores of teachers and the 50% of the highest possible score that can obtained from the questionnaire was measured. Moreover, Mann Whitney U test was done to measure how gender effects the scores of teachers. Also, descriptive statistics were made to measure central tendencies (mean, median, mode) and skewness of the distribution of the total scores of teachers. Finally, Kruskal Wallis test was made to measure how age effects the scores of teachers.

Results and Discussion

The sample consisted of 42 men and 34 women. According to the data obtained from demographic information form, 50 participants in the sample took a vocational ethics course. Moreover, in this research, we have created 4 group for the defining the ages which were 20-30 age group, 31-40 age group, 41-50 age group and 51 and 51 above. It is found that the majority of the participants were between 20-30 years old and only two participants were 51 or over the 51 years old. According to these analyzes, it was found that teachers who has an inclusive student in their classroom insufficient in the application of vocational ethics in their classroom. Also, it was realized that gender has no effect on the attitudes of preschool teachers on vocational ethics.

In the study conducted by Duran (2014) to determine the level of perception of professional ethical behaviors of preschool teachers; Ethical behavior perceptions of

preschool teachers were high. However, it was found that teachers' perception of ethical behaviors did not change according to age and professional seniority (Duran,2014). In addition, it was found that teachers' perceptions of ethical behavior differed statistically significantly according to the department they graduated from, their postgraduate education status and the type of institution they work for (Duran,2014). The result of the research is similar to the findings of our study.

Table 1. Descriptive Features of Total Scores

Descriptive Statistics

	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
						Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
SMEAN (TOTAL)	76	28	115	46.21	14.341	2.185	.276	7.192	.545
Valid N (listwise)	76								

In the Table 1., it is found that minimum score of the completed questionnaire was 28 and the maximum score was 115. According to the descriptive analyzes the mean of the obtained data was 46.21 while the 50% of the highest possible score that can be obtained from the questionnaire was 70. Therefore, it was realized that total mean were lower than expected mean. Also, it is realized that skewness and kurtosis statistics (2.185, 7,192) were higher than +1.0 which means that sum of the scores are not distributed normally. The distribution of the sum of data was positively skewed. According to Hair et al. (2013) skewness and kurtosis statistics must be between +1.0 and -1.0 to call a data set normally distributed. Thus in hypothesis thesis nonparametric statistical tests.

Table 2. The Differences Between Total Scores of Teachers According to Age

Ranks

	SMEAN(AGE)	N	Mean Rank
SMEAN	20-30	49	42.84
(TOTAL)	31-40	19	33.50
	41-50	6	28.33
	51+	2	10.25
	Total	76	

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	SMEAN (TOTAL)
Chi-Square	7.427
df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.059

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable:
SMEAN(AGE)

According to Table 2, majority of the participants were between 20-30 years old and only two participants were 51 or over the 51 years old. Also, according to the results, the mean of total scores was the highest in the 20–30 age group. In the 51+ age group, the mean of total scores was the lowest. According to the Table 2., the differences between total scores of teachers according to age was not found significant. The Asymp. Sig. (.059) was higher than .05 ($P > .05$) which means that age has no significant impact on the perception of the teachers on vocational ethics. In this regard, Aydemir (2012) revealed that the views of preschool teachers on professional ethical behaviors do not differ according to the age variable. Similar findings are seen in the study of Duran (2014). When compared with the research results in the literature, it is seen that the results of this research are similar. Ethical behavior perceptions of teachers do not differ with age.

Table 3. Differences Between Total Scores of Teachers According to Gender

<i>Ranks</i>					<i>Test Statistics^a</i>	
						SMEAN (TOTAL)
	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann-Whitney U	568.500
SMEAN (TOTAL)	Male	42	41.96	1762.50	Wilcoxon W	1163.500
	Female	34	34.22	1163.50	Z	-1.522
	Total	76			Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.128

a. Grouping Variable: Gender

According to Table 4. means of the scores changes between gender. The mean score of the males were higher than females. However, the difference was not found significant because the Asymp. Sig. (.128) was higher than .05 ($P > 0.05$). Thus, it was concluded that gender has no effect on the perception of the teachers on vocational ethics. According to Ay (2005); Culture, personal characteristics, gender, age, religion, profession and organizational activities affect the ethical decision-making processes of individuals. However, as in our study, Aydemir's (2012) study on Preschool Teachers' Views on Professional Ethical Behaviors found that teachers' views on professional ethical behaviors are not affected by age, marital status, socio-economic level, graduated institution, type of school, number of children owned and fathers' education (Aydemir, 2012; Uzun & Elma, 2012).

Table 4. Differences Between the Score of the Teachers and 50% of the Highest Possible Score that can Obtained From the Questionnaire

<i>Frequencies</i>		N	<i>Test Statistics^a</i>	
Median - SMEAN (TOTAL)	Negative Differences ^a	5	Z	Median - SMEAN (TOTAL)
	Positive Differences ^b	71		
	Ties ^c	0		
	Total	76		
a. Median < SMEAN(TOTAL)			Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)	
b. Median > SMEAN(TOTAL)			-7.456	
c. Median = SMEAN(TOTAL)			.000	
			a. Sign Test	

In analyzing the variables, sign test was used instead of the one-sample T test due to the distribution of the data. Population median and expected mean was 70, the 50% of the highest possible score that can obtained from the questionnaire according to the hypothesis. According to the Table 3. the number of total scores which is lower than the median is higher which means that the score of the teachers are lower than expected. Also, according to the test statistics, it was found that Asymp. Sig. (.000) was lower than the .05 ($P < .05$). Thus, it was concluded that the difference between expected mean (median) and total score of teachers were significant.

Statistics results show us that preschool teachers are not sufficient in ethics. This may be due to the fact that teachers have students with special needs in their classrooms. In a study conducted by Tezcan and Güvenç (2020) on this subject, it is found that teachers face ethical dilemmas about behaving fairly and equally in classes with students with special needs, which is in line with the results of the research. In addition, Öztürk (2010) in his study on pre-school teachers' views on ethical principles; emphasized that responsibilities of preschool teachers should be accepting children as individuals and behave respectfully to their personalities, and that some precautions should be taken especially for children with special needs.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Professional ethics are really important to achieve professional goals and work effectively. Especially, occupations that based on communication with people such as teaching, Professional ethics are really beneficial to solve problems at work places. However, sometimes teachers have difficulty to apply professional ethics at works. According to the literature review, teachers who have inclusive student in their

classroom feel more difficulty to apply Professional ethics than other teachers (Tezcan & Güvenç, 2020).

In this research, the perspectives of preschool teachers who have students with special needs in their classroom on ethics was examined. According to the result of the study, it was found that teachers who has an inclusive student in their classroom were insufficient in the application of vocational ethics in their classroom. Also, it was realized that gender has no effect on the attitudes of preschool teachers on vocational ethics which is in line with the hypothesis of this research. Moreover, just like gender, age does not have an effect on the scores obtained form teachers.

It is suggested that vocational ethics courses must be obligatory in preschool teachers traning programbecause preschool teachers who has an inclusive student in their classroom can face ethical dilemmas in their classroom. Also, it can be suggested to teachers to get supervision from an expert when they face an ethical dilemma and don't know what to do. Moreover, schools can support their teachers by giving them opportunities to improve their knowledge about applying vocational ethics such as organizing seminars, contacting with people who are expert in vocational ethics.

References

- Akçamete, G., Kayhan, N., İçsen-Karasu, F., Sardoohan-Yıldırım, A. E., & Şen, M. (2016). Professional ethical principles for special education teachers. *SDU International Journal of Educational Studies*, 3(1), 27-44. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/sduijes/issue/20865/223879>
- Arslan, M. (2018). *Meslek Etiği ve Öğretmenlik Meslek Etiğine İlişkin Öğretmen Görüşlerinin Belirlenmesi*. Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Akdeniz Üniversitesi. Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Eğitim Bilimleri Anabilim Dalı, Antalya.
- Ay, C. (2005). İşletmelerde etiksel karar almada kültürün rolü. *Yönetim ve Ekonomi*, 12(2), 31–52.
- Aydemir, F. (2012). *Okul Öncesi Öğretmenlerinin Mesleki Etik Davranışlar Hakkındaki Görüşlerinin İncelenmesi*. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Malatya.
- Aydın, İ. (2006). *Eğitim ve öğretimde etik*. (İkinci baskı). Ankara: Pegem A Yayıncılık.
- Baydar, T. (2005). Yönetim Etiğine Genel Bakış. *Türk idare dergisi*, Sayı:449,2005.
- Bir, A.B. (2019). *Özel Eğitim Öğretmenleri İçin Mesleki Etik İlkelerinin İncelenmesi*. KKTC Yakın Doğu Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü Özel Eğitim Anabilim Dalı. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi.

- Cavkaytar, A. (2017). *Özel Eğitime Gereksinim Duyan Çocuklar ve Özel Eğitim*. Diken, İ.H. (Ed.), *Özel Eğitime Gereksinim Duyan Çocuklar ve Özel Eğitim*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi Yayınları.
- Deniz, E. & Çoban, A. (2019). Kaynaştırma Eğitimine İlişkin Öğretmen Görüşleri. *Electronic Journal of Social Sciences*, 18(70), 734–761.
- Diken, İ.H. & Batu, S. (2015). *Kaynaştırmaya Giriş, İlköğretimde Kaynaştırma*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi Yayınları.
- Duran, K. (2014). *Okul Öncesi Öğretmenlerinin Mesleki Etik Davranışları Algılama Düzeylerinin ve Etik İnkilemleri Çözümlemelerinin İncelenmesi*. Hacettepe Üniversitesi İlköğretim Anabilim Dalı, Okul Öncesi Eğitimi Bilim Dalı Yüksek Lisans Tezi.
- Flew, A. (2005). *Felsefe sözlüğü*. (Çeviren: Nurşen Özsoy). İstanbul: Yeryüzü Yayınevi.
- Girgin, İ. (2021). Eğitimcilerin Kaynaştırmaya Yönelik Mesleki Gelişim İhtiyaçları. *Uluslararası Toplum Araştırmaları Dergisi-International Journal of Society Research*. 18(11), 4151–4175.
- Hair, J.F., Black, W.C., Babin, B.J., Anderson, R.E., & Tatham, R.L. (2013). *Multivariate Data Analysis: Pearson Education Limited.7 Edition*.
- Kepenek, Ö. (2008). *Öğretmenlik Meslek Etik İlkelerinin Örgütsel Vatandaşlık Davranışına Etkisi (Kocaeli İli Örneği)*. Sakarya Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü. Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Sakarya.
- MEB (2006). *Meslek etiği kitabı. Megep (Meslekî Eğitim ve Öğretim Sisteminin Güçlendirilmesi Projesi) Tüm Alanlar*, Ankara. MEB. Genelge. Eğitimciler için mesleki etik ilkeler. <http://www.meb.gov.tr>, adresinden erişildi. (ET: 23.03.2019).
- Moreno, J.A.C., Jaén, M.D.M., Navío, E.P., & Moreno, J.R. (2015). Inclusive education in schools in rural ares. *New Approaches in Educational Research*, 4(2), 107–114.
- NEA (2011). NEA Handbook. Washington: National Education Association. http://www.nea.org/assets/docs/2011_NEA_Handbook_nea-org.pdf adresinden 15.05.2019 tarihinde erişilmiştir.
- Özdemir, O. (2022). Özel Eğitimde Etik ve Etik Değerlendirmeler. *Ankara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Fakültesi Özel Eğitim Dergisi*, 23(1), 219–241.
- Öztürk, Ş. (2010). Okul Öncesi Öğretmenlerinin Etik İlkelerle İlgili Görüşleri. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Bilimleri / Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 10 (1), 365–418.
- Tezcan, G. and Güvenç, H. (2020). Ortaokul Öğretmenlerinin Mesleki Etik İnkilemleri. *Pamukkale Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 49, 439–460.
- Uzun, E.M. & Elma, C.(2012). Okul Öncesi Öğretmenlerinin Mesleki Etik İnkilemleri Çözümleme Biçimleri. *Journal of Research in Education and Teaching*, 1(3).

